

Erratum

Erratum to “Investigating the Transferability of Calibrated Microsimulation Parameters for Operational Performance Analysis in Roundabouts”

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In the article titled “Investigating the Transferability of Calibrated Microsimulation Parameters for Operational Performance Analysis in Roundabouts” [1], there was an error in reference [17], which should be corrected as follows:

- [17] R. Arroju, H. K. Gaddam, L. D. Vanumu, and K. Ramachandra Rao, “Comparative evaluation of roundabout capacities under heterogeneous traffic conditions,” *Journal of Modern Transportation*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 310–324, 2015.

The reference has been corrected in the article.

References

- [1] V. Gallelli, T. Iuele, R. Vaiana, and A. Vitale, “Investigating the transferability of calibrated microsimulation parameters for operational performance analysis in roundabouts,” *Journal of Advanced Transportation*, vol. 2017, Article ID 3078063, 10 pages, 2017.

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